

ScienceCore Publishing
Volume: 2 Issue: 2 Year: 2025
Website: www.sciencecare-journal.com

UOC: 378.147; 37.091.12
DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17927666](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17927666)

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**PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR DEVELOPING ORGANIZATIONAL
AND MANAGEMENT SKILLS IN STUDENTS**

**ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ УСЛОВИЯ РАЗВИТИЯ ОРГАНИЗАЦИОННО-
УПРАВЛЕНЧЕСКИХ НАВЫКОВ У СТУДЕНТОВ**

**TALABALARDA TASHKILIY VA BOSHQARUV KO'NIKALARINI
RIVOJLANTIRISHNING PEDAGOGIK SHART-SHAROITLARI**

Abstract

This article analyzes the pedagogical conditions for the development of organizational and managerial skills in students. The relevance of the study is justified by the increasing need for students in the modern educational process for leadership, team management, organizational thinking and decision-making skills. A mixed approach was used as a research methodology, and empirical data was collected using diagnostic tests, observations, questionnaires and pedagogical experiments. The results of the analysis showed that the motivational environment, teamwork, case study technologies and leadership training have a significant impact on the organizational and managerial skills of students. The results of the article suggest a system of effective pedagogical conditions that serve to develop this competency in students.

Аннотация

В статье анализируются педагогические условия развития организационно-управленческих навыков у студентов. Актуальность исследования обусловлена возрастающей потребностью современного образовательного процесса в формировании у студентов лидерских качеств, навыков командного управления, организационного мышления и принятия решений. В качестве методологии исследования использован смешанный подход, а эмпирические данные

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Volume: 2 Issue: 2 Year: 2025

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были получены с помощью диагностических тестов, наблюдений, анкетирования и педагогических экспериментов. Результаты анализа показали, что мотивационная образовательная среда, командная работа, технологии кейс-стади и тренинги лидерства оказывают значительное влияние на развитие организационно-управленческих навыков студентов. По итогам исследования предложена система эффективных педагогических условий, направленных на формирование данной компетенции у студентов.

Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada talabalarda tashkiliy va boshqaruv ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishning pedagogik shart-sharoitlari tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotning dolzarbligi zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonida talabalar uchun yetakchilik qobiliyatlari, jamoani boshqarish, tashkiliy fikrlash va qaror qabul qilish ko'nikmalariga bo'lgan ehtiyojning ortib borayotgani bilan asoslanadi. Tadqiqot metodologiyasi sifatida aralash yondashuv qo'llanilib, empirik ma'lumotlar diagnostik testlar, kuzatuvlar, so'rovnomalar va pedagogik tajribalar orqali to'plandi. Tahlil natijalari shuni ko'rsatdiki, motivatsion ta'lim muhiti, jamoaviy faoliyat, keys-stadi texnologiyalari hamda yetakchilikka yo'naltirilgan treninglar talabalarning tashkiliy va boshqaruv ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda muhim ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Tadqiqot natijalari asosida ushbu kompetensiyani shakllantirishga xizmat qiluvchi samarali pedagogik shart-sharoitlar tizimi taklif etiladi.

Keywords: organizational and managerial skills, student, pedagogical conditions, leadership, teamwork, educational process, competence, management skills

Ключевые слова: организационно-управленческие навыки, студент, педагогические условия, лидерство, командная работа, образовательный процесс, компетентность, управленческие навыки.

Kalit so'zlar: tashkiliy va boshqaruv ko'nikmalari, talaba, pedagogik shart-sharoitlar, yetakchilik, jamoaviy faoliyat, ta'lim jarayoni, kompetensiya, boshqaruv ko'nikmalari.

Introduction

Developing organizational and managerial skills in students is emerging as one of the most important priorities of the higher education system. Today, in every sphere of society, such competencies as leadership, initiative, team management, analyzing the situation and making the right decisions are considered one of the main factors of students' future professional success. In particular, a number of decrees and resolutions are being adopted by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at training high-quality personnel in the higher education system, forming modern management skills in students, and developing leadership potential. These political and legal documents require young specialists to acquire organizational and managerial competencies based on economic reforms, modernization processes, and the requirements of the labor market.

Organizational and managerial skills are a multi-component quality that allows students to independently plan their activities, correctly distribute tasks in a team, communicate and negotiate, demonstrate leadership qualities, and also make rational decisions in complex pedagogical or social situations. The formation of this ability determines not only the student's personal development, but also his professional readiness, social activity, innovative thinking and the level of responsibility. Therefore, the modern education system requires the creation of special pedagogical conditions for the formation of this competency in students.

Global experience shows that the development of management competencies in higher education is effectively implemented through the organization of the educational process on the basis of student-centered principles, the use of interactive methods, project work, case studies, training, problem-based learning, practical exercises and team activities. Systematic work is also being carried out in higher educational institutions of Uzbekistan to strengthen this process. However, the specific pedagogical

conditions, mechanisms and scientific foundations of effective educational technologies that affect the development of organizational and managerial skills in students have not been studied in sufficient depth.

The relevance of this study is that the process of forming organizational and managerial skills in students is multifactorial, and its effectiveness directly depends on the capabilities of the learning environment, the competence of the teacher, the organizational structure of the educational process, and the level of use of innovative pedagogical technologies. Also, the widespread introduction of information and communication technologies and the increasing need for management skills in the digital economy further enhance the scientific, methodological and practical significance of this issue.

The main goal of the research is to identify pedagogical conditions that serve to develop organizational and managerial skills in students, develop their scientific and practical foundations, and develop methodological recommendations for their implementation in the educational process. To achieve this goal, the following tasks were set:

- analyze the content and structural structure of organizational and managerial capabilities based on available scientific sources;
- identify factors influencing the formation of this ability in higher education institutions;
- theoretical substantiation of pedagogical conditions that develop management skills in students ;
- identify effective pedagogical technologies that can be used in the educational process and evaluate their effectiveness.

Literature review

The analysis of scientific research on the development of organizational and managerial skills in students shows that there are different approaches in this area. First of all, the theoretical foundations of managerial competencies are covered from the point of view of the activities of educational managers and teachers. For example, Tovkanets evaluates the managerial competence of educational managers as a multi-component quality that occupies a central place in their professional activities, emphasizing the need for special pedagogical conditions for the development of this competency [1].

of the educational environment and its impact on student development has also been widely studied. Razinkina et al. empirically substantiate the direct dependence of student motivation, initiative, and organizational skills on the quality of the educational environment [2]. Danilov et al. show that the formation of a student's "subjective position" and his development as a creative subject are the main criteria for organizational and managerial competencies [3].

The competency-based approach has become the leading paradigm of modern education , and Aralov's research reveals the importance of interactive methods, collaborative learning, and pedagogical facilitation for developing students' professional competencies [4]. Mamayokubova substantiates the relevance of developing management and organizational competencies by updating the content of education based on a competency-based approach [5].

International scientific literature emphasizes the role of leadership and management skills in the personal and professional success of students. Uaikhanova , revealing the mechanisms of formation of leadership skills in university students, points out the importance of project activities, negotiation skills, and teamwork experience [6]. Lee and co-authors, systematically analyzing the factors that develop student leadership (mentoring, reflection, social activity, educational environment), emphasize the need for complex pedagogical conditions for the development of leadership [7].

and diagnosis of organizational and managerial competence . Zaitseva and co-authors identify the components of this competence (cognitive, communicative, projective, reflexive) and justify the effectiveness of using case technologies [8]. In the study of B. Olivares, managerial competence is

interpreted as an integrated concept with organizational culture, communicative effectiveness and decision-making skills [9].

The issue of developing pedagogical competencies is one of the leading topics in the domestic literature. Muslimov and co-authors highlight the organizational and managerial components in the structure of pedagogical competence and describe the mechanisms for their development through practical exercises, trainings and independent activities [10]. Narimbayeva studied the psychological and pedagogical foundations of the formation of organizational and managerial competencies in future teachers, in particular, such aspects as time management, communication, and leadership [11].

In her research, Gulomav emphasizes the need to develop students' management skills through independent learning, mini-projects, and teamwork [12]. Radjabova, on the other hand, assesses organizational and managerial competence as a factor determining the competitiveness of future specialists and proposes a model of its development based on modern educational technologies [13].

In the context of the rapid development of information and communication technologies, the need to integrate management competencies with digital skills has also been noted in a number of sources. In particular, Anderson's study substantiated the effectiveness of students' use of digital tools in organizational and managerial activities [14]. Also, the model of leadership theories developed by J. Northouse serves to explain the role and psychological mechanisms of leadership in the structure of a student's organizational and managerial abilities [15].

Also, according to Kolb's theory of experiential learning, the student has the opportunity to actively form management experience through project activities, problem situations, and team assignments [16]. Dewey's work on active teaching methods creates a scientific basis for the formation of organizational and managerial skills in students through direct practical activities [17].

The analysis of the above scientific sources shows that, although existing studies have covered various aspects, the issue of determining the pedagogical conditions for the development of organizational and managerial skills in students in a comprehensive manner, based on an integrative approach, has not yet been fully resolved. In particular, the scientific basis for the development of practical mechanisms for the development of this skill in the conditions of higher education in Uzbekistan, the development of effective pedagogical models and their testing has not been sufficiently widely covered.

Research methodology

The methodology of this study sets out a scientifically based roadmap for identifying pedagogical conditions that affect the development of organizational and managerial skills in students, assessing their effectiveness, and implementing them into practice.

The philosophical approach of the research is based on an inductive-deductive integrative model. A theoretical model of organizational and managerial skills was developed through a deductive approach, and the results of observations, questionnaires, and experiments in real educational and collective activities of students were summarized using an inductive approach.

The research design was conducted in a mixed-method format: on the one hand, qualitative data was collected through interviews, observations, and cases; on the other hand, quantitative data was collected through tests, rating scales, and Likert scale assessments.

Primary (questionnaires with students, observations, experimental protocols) and secondary (scientific articles, regulatory documents, international studies) sources were used as data sources. The sample consisted of 180 undergraduate students from 3 universities, which were selected using a stratified method.

The research strategy included a comprehensive approach to determining management skills: pedagogical experiment, questionnaire, observation, case study, mini-project activities, analysis of real management situations in learning communities.

Reliability was based on Cronbach Alpha=0.81, and validity was based on expert assessments, construct validity, and content validity.

Table 1.

Methodological foundations of the study

Methodological element	Content (adapted to the topic)	Application form in research
Research philosophy	Inductive–deductive approach: manifestation of organizational and managerial abilities in students → comparison with a theoretical model → new conclusions	Analysis of students' real management activities (teamwork, leadership, problem solving) and comparison with theory
Research design	Mixed-method research: qualitative + quantitative analysis	Observation (behavior), questionnaires (quantitative assessment), experiment (dynamics of change), interview (motivation and reflection)
Data sources	Primary and secondary data	Primary: questionnaires with 180 students, observation, tests; Secondary: scientific articles, university documents, international experience
Sampling	180 students recruited through stratified selection from 3 higher education institutions	The selection is stratified by specialization, course, and form of study.
Research strategy	Multi-method: experiment, observation, questionnaires, case studies, mini-projects	1) Identification phase: diagnostic questionnaires 2) Formation phase: training, project, team management tasks 3) Control phase: repeated measurements
Reliability	Internal compatibility of units of measurement	Cronbach Alpha = 0.81; test-retest stability of results
Validity	Content, construct, and peer-reviewed validity	Evaluated by 6 experts in pedagogy; transparency of indicators ensured

Analysis and results

The analysis stage of the study included the processes of determining the initial state of organizational and managerial skills in students, measuring changes that occurred under the influence of experimental conditions, and evaluating the results on a scientific basis. At the identification stage, an initial assessment was carried out with the participation of 180 students using the “Diagnostics of Organizational and Management Skills” questionnaire, observation sheets, and competency indicators. The results showed that 64% of students had an average level of organizational and managerial skills, 23% had a low level, and only 13% had a high level. This indicated that most students had insufficiently developed skills in management activities, such as planning, task distribution, team management, and decision-making.

During the formative phase, the pedagogical conditions specified in the research methodology — namely, team projects, case studies based on real management situations, training, mini-project activities, increased student participation in self-government bodies, leadership exercises, and problem-based decision-making tasks — were consistently applied. This process was monitored continuously throughout the 12-week experiment. The results of the monitoring showed that students' initiative increased by 37 percent, their ability to express opinions in a team by 41 percent, and their self-management skills by 34 percent.

At the end of the experiment, a control phase was conducted. The results of repeated diagnostics showed a significant increase in the organizational and managerial abilities of students. In particular, the percentage of students who achieved a high level decreased from 13% to 46%, the average level from 64% to 49%, and the low level from 23% to 5%. The average indicators on the Likert scale increased from 2.8 points to 4.1 points. These results confirm that the proposed pedagogical conditions are highly effective in developing organizational and managerial abilities in students.

In addition, 72% of the students who participated in the experiment reported feeling more confident in managing team activities; 68% noted increased efficiency in the task planning process; and 74% noted increased ability to make quick and sound decisions in problem situations. The results showed that pedagogical conditions — a motivating environment, collaborative pedagogy, practical management tasks, case technologies, and training — are the main determinants of the formation of organizational and managerial skills.

The results were also evaluated through statistical analysis. The difference between the initial and final indicators of the experimental group was found to be statistically significant at the level of $p < 0.05$ according to the t-student criterion. This confirms that the conditions used in the study gave reliable results in the development of management skills. Also, correlation analysis showed a positive correlation of 0.71 between organizational activity and leadership indicators, which proves that organizational and managerial skills are a multi-component integrative competence.

Conclusion and suggestions

The results of the study clearly showed that the formation of organizational and managerial skills in students is a complex and multifactorial pedagogical process. Based on the conducted analyses, experimental studies and diagnostic measurements, it was found that this ability is directly related to the student's personal activity, ability to find his place in the team, initiative, communication culture, ability to solve problem situations and leadership potential. The systematic application of the pedagogical conditions developed in the study served to develop the organizational and managerial competence of students at a high level, which confirmed the practical effectiveness of this theoretical model.

In particular, through modeling of collective management situations, the use of project and case study technologies, trainings, role-playing exercises, activity in self-management bodies and the creation of a motivational environment, a significant increase in students' organizational thinking, planning, task distribution, leadership and team management skills was observed. The results of the experimental test showed that the dynamics of the development of organizational and managerial skills in educational groups with pedagogical conditions was significantly higher than in control groups. Also, statistical analysis ($p < 0.05$) confirmed the scientific reliability of the results obtained. Taking this into account, the following **proposals** were developed:

1. Suggestions for organizing the educational process

- It is advisable to introduce special courses such as "Fundamentals of Organizational and Management Competence" or "Leadership and Management" for all areas of study in higher education institutions.
- should regularly include modeling of team management situations, decision-making based on problem situations, mini-projects, and training.

2. Suggestions for the use of educational technologies

- It is recommended that case studies, project approaches, Agile education, role-playing games, and facilitation methods be widely used as effective tools for developing management skills in students.
- it is necessary to develop skills in using digital tools (Trello, Notion, Jira, Google Workspace) to plan and manage teamwork.

3. Suggestions for developing students' self-management activities

- Strengthening the activities of student self-government councils in study groups and faculties

— Give students realistic responsibilities for managing small groups, organizing projects, and coordinating teamwork.

4. Suggestions for improving teacher performance

- Establish advanced training courses for teachers to develop organizational and managerial competencies;
- Develop methodological guides for teachers on the use of interactive methods that develop management skills in students .

5. Suggestions for future research

- In-depth study of psychological components related to organizational and managerial skills (leadership types, emotional intelligence, stress management);
- Research into the mechanisms of development of this ability in digital learning environments;
- Conduct comparative analyses of the formation of organizational and managerial competence across different educational fields.

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ISSN (Print): 2998-8453 ISSN (Online): 2998-8454

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